

Socio-Psychological Features of Students with Special Educational Needs as a Cause of Conflicts in Inclusive Groups

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Abstract: *The article examines the causes of conflicts in inclusive student groups and means of their prevention. It has been found that the success of inclusive education in higher education institutions mainly depends on interpersonal relationships in inclusive student groups. This is due to the fact that communicating with each other, students with special educational needs acquire skills of social interaction, widen the range of their social roles, learn more about their own personality. However, the peculiarities of moral attitudes, values, behavior, features of the emotional and volitional sphere development, cognitive processes of students with special educational needs lead to conflict situations in inclusive student groups. To determine the causes of conflicts in inclusive student groups, a diagnostic study was conducted among the full-time and part-time students with special educational needs of Khmelnytsky National University. The results of the diagnosis showed that main causes of conflicts in inclusive student groups are the following socio-psychological characteristics of students with special educational needs: low level of self-esteem due to which they get painful experiences because of critical remarks addressed to them, try to adapt to other people's opinions, have low motivation for achievement, feel lonely and anxious; low ability to establish new contacts for communication, low level of sociability; the desire to avoid conflict or to get out of it with dignity accepting the opinions and interests of others without seeking compromise solutions. Taking this into consideration, we have developed and substantiated conflict prevention tools for inclusive student groups that can help students with special educational needs to interact effectively with other students while studying at higher education institution.*

Keywords: *students with special educational needs; inclusive education; higher educational institution; conflicts in inclusive student groups.*

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Introduction

As the number of people with special educational needs, especially children, in developed countries is increasing, disability prevention and social problems solution have become the national priorities of these countries. The problem of education of children and youth with special educational needs has always been the most complicated problem for the society. Nowadays, inclusive education is supposed to solve it, as it recognizes the necessity to meet the various demands and abilities of children and youth with special educational needs, including differences in ways and tempo of learning. This goal is achieved by means of individualized teaching methods, adapted curricula and individually selected learning support materials. Inclusive education is a necessary condition for active adaptation, socialization and development of students with special educational needs.

Inclusion is considered to be a process of increasing the participation of people with special educational needs in social life, and inclusive education is defined as a system of educational services based on the principle of ensuring the basic right of children to education and the right to receive it at the place of residence at secondary education institution which is adjusted to the needs of all students (Sophii, 2008).

The success of the inclusive education implementation largely depends on the interpersonal relationships in the student group. Starting their studying, students begin a new independent life, which is an integral part of the higher education institution where they study and the group which they belong to. The new relationships, formed in the group, are based on the commitment or unfriendliness of some students to others, which can lead to conflicts.

The term "conflict" means "collision". Conflict arises when people begin to realize that their interests, needs, goals can not be met if the existing system of social relations is maintained, and begin to act trying to change the situation (Tiuptya, 2008).

A number of scientists studied some aspects of involvement of children and youth with special educational needs into studying at regular educational institutions, their rehabilitation and socialization to social rules: (Kolupaeva et al., 2012; Talanchuk et al., 2004; Chaikovsky, 2016).

The problem of causes and ways of resolving conflicts in inclusive classrooms and inclusive student groups was covered by the studies of Volchelyuk (2010), Lavrinenko (2017), Popeliushko, (2019) and Romanovska & Vasylenko (2020).

The important role of teachers in the inclusive education implementation and solving all related problems is discussed in the works of the following researchers: Mățã & Clipa (2020); Bezliudnyi et al. (2020); Frumos (2020); Sălceanu (2020).

Thus, Mățã & Clipa (2020) argue that it is extremely important to study the attitude of teachers to the integration of students with special educational needs in secondary schools. This will help to identify appropriate measures of influence to establish a relationship based on mutual trust and support of equal learning opportunities for all the educational process participants. If teachers have a positive attitude towards an inclusive school, they become more open to adapting and changing teaching methods to meet the needs of students with special educational needs.

Chaikovsky (2016) stresses that inclusive education is closely interrelated with the integration process of people with special educational needs into the social and educational environment, which is defined as the normalization of social life and educational opportunities in accordance with international and Ukrainian legal acts. However, one of the most important aspects of the inclusive education implementation in higher education institutions is the inclusive competence of higher education teachers. The author defines it as a relatively independent part of general professional competence; integrative personal education, which determines the ability to perform educational functions in the inclusive education process, in particular to meet the educational needs of students with special educational needs, their socio-pedagogical adaptation in the educational environment, to create all conditions for their development.

The works of Bezliudnyi et al. (2020) concluded that current researches on inclusive education focus mainly on the following aspects: identifying the peculiarities of interaction between primary school teachers and students' parents in inclusive practice; the requirements and the role of the teacher who works with students with special educational needs; behavior of parents of students with special educational needs. The authors believe that future teachers must be specially trained in various aspects of inclusive practice. Unfortunately, the theoretical and applied aspects of such training are insufficiently developed, which indicates a certain inefficiency of teacher training for the inclusive education implementation.

A Romanian scientist (Frumos, 2020) believes that teachers who work in inclusive classrooms take on new roles and responsibilities as they have to meet the needs of all students in the classroom. These teachers must be committed to the principles of inclusion, accept all the challenges of inclusive education and try to develop curricula taking into account the

capabilities of all students, regardless of their abilities, psychophysiological characteristics, etc. In case of distance learning, the transition to inclusive education in the online classroom is possible and necessary. A student with special educational needs should participate in an online environment for a wide range of learning activities. But some limitations are still infeasible, so teachers must actively overcome them, using various tools and methods. At the same time, teachers should be responsible for the choice and use of certain methods and training resources in accordance with the needs of students, so that the latter can achieve basic educational goals.

Sălceanu (2020) emphasizes the important role of teachers in the inclusion of autistic children in public schools. It is the teacher who plays an active role in the development of children's cognitive, practical and social skills, in the management of children's classes and in creating opportunities for learning for both ordinary and autistic children. To achieve their goals, teachers need training, resources and support from an interdisciplinary team of specialists. Unfortunately, quite often teachers refuse to work with autistic children, especially because they lack sufficient training to be able to provide an inclusive environment for such children. Many teachers have fear that they will not be able to manage the classroom well enough, and having an autistic child can be a problem for other children. Therefore, the success of including children with autism in regular educational institutions depends on the teachers' efforts, their positive attitude to inclusive education, openness and development of their own professional skills. This should be combined with an acceptance and a positive attitude of children and their parents to the autistic child, the intervention of specialists (facilitators, therapists, counselors, psychologists). It is also the teacher who should raise awareness and sensitivity towards children with autism in parents of ordinary children, school board and classmates, by means of organizing classes with social workers, psychologists and other professionals to familiarize everyone with the needs of autistic children. Such educational programs can lead to a change in attitudes towards autistic children and their isolation.

Ukrainian scientist Teslenko (2020) argues that Ukrainian social pedagogy is just taking the first steps in the scientific substantiation of the content, forms and methods of social and pedagogical support for children with special educational needs. Therefore, in his research, he pays special attention to the development of conceptual approaches to social and pedagogical support of children with special educational needs, as well as the stages of implementation of this support. The experience of experimental organization of social and educational support, rehabilitation and social adaptation of children with special educational needs in Ukraine allows the

author to conclude that timely and early social and educational support is a priority in the development of life skills of children with special educational needs. It creates a favorable rehabilitation environment and takes into account the most productive age for rehabilitation and social adaptation. Thus, V. Teslenko proposes to develop and implement regional programs of social and educational support for children with special educational needs. It should look like a scientific algorithm that provides a logical sequence and step-by-step actions of all providers of social and educational support for children with special educational needs. According to the author, the regional program provides effective assistance to each family on the basis of a complete database of legal, social, economic, medical, psychological and pedagogical support of the interests and requests of the child and their further self-determination in public life.

Ukrainian researcher Vasylenko (2010) supporting Teslenko's opinion, states that the adaptation of children with special educational needs to study in regular educational institutions will be more effective if the following social and pedagogical conditions are introduced in the institutions: arranging of a favorable social and educational environment for students with special educational needs; development of productive relationship types of the child with special educational needs with others (in the classroom, in the family); organization of socio-pedagogical and psychological assistance to a family raising a child with special educational needs.

Popeliushko (2019) believes that attending regular school classes together with their peers, leads to positive personal changes of the students with special educational needs. The author notes that higher education institutions as social institutions should be involved in the promotion and implementation of inclusive education. They must adopt their own concept of inclusive learning (special education services can be provided in different settings) and support the learning of each student with special educational needs (teachers can teach in three ways: firstly, their way of teaching must be clear to the students with different abilities and learning styles so that they could understand the learning process and take an active part in it; secondly, teachers change tasks when they are too difficult for students with special educational needs; third, they model respect and encourage friendship between students in an academic group).

However, despite the interest of researchers in the implementation of inclusive education in educational institutions at all levels and solving the issues related to this process, it needs to be studied more detailly. The nature of the interpersonal relationship development in an inclusive classroom and

an inclusive student group determines not only the academic success of children and youth with special educational needs, but also the effectiveness of their adaptation, socialization and rehabilitation.

Research problem

Scientists claim that the work of specialists in educational institutions is very important, because it is focused on involving children and youth with special educational needs in the educational process, their socialization, developing their active attitude to confident self-positioning in society, obtaining the skill to transform their weaknesses into strengths, changing the attitude of modern society to people with special educational needs. However, the implementation of inclusive education has a number of obstacles, including psychological rejection of students with disabilities by other students. This factor, unfortunately, is one of the dominant causes of conflicts in inclusive student groups of higher education institutions.

Therefore, the purpose of this article is to study the socio-psychological features of students with special educational needs that lead to conflicts in inclusive student groups, and to develop means to prevent these conflicts.

Methods and stages of research

The diagnostic study involved 55 students with special educational needs of Khmelnytskyi National University: 15 students majoring "Psychology", 15 students of "Social Work", 11 students "Philology" students and 14 "Secondary Education" students. The age of participants taking part in the diagnostic study was 18-22 years. They provided their verbal consent to participate in the study and process the results of the study without disclosing personal information about them. Students worked with questionnaires in their free time.

The study was carried out within the theme of the research work of the Department of Psychology and Pedagogy of Khmelnytskyi National University "Transformation of the human vital world in terms of personal and professional development". The study was conducted in several stages from September to December, 2020).

The first stage of the study was conducted to determine the causes of conflict in inclusive student groups.

The aim of the second stage of the study was to diagnose those socio-psychological features of students with special educational needs that lead to conflicts in inclusive student groups. For this purpose the following

diagnostic methods were used as: test-questionnaire "Self-assessment scale"; anxiety test (Spielberg Questionnaire); method "Assessment of the sociability level" (V. Ryakhovsky); questionnaire to determine the level of student youth socialization; K. Thomas test (adaptation by N. Grishina, 2008).

The third stage of the study was carried out to analyze the results of diagnosis of socio-psychological features of students with special educational needs that lead to conflicts in inclusive student groups, and development and justification of means to prevent such conflicts.

Study Results

In a higher education institution, the student group plays the most important role in the students' socialization. Communicating with each other, students acquire skills of social interaction, widen their range of social roles, learn more about their own personality. Differences in moral attitudes, rules, values, behavior often put the student in a conflict situation. The academic group works out specific relationships, standards and norms of behavior, values and socio-psychological climate. The collision of different tendencies in intentions, attitudes, motives and behavior can lead to conflict. So, conflicts become an integral part of student life (Bogdanov, 2004).

It is worth noting that in inclusive student groups, the causes of conflict can be low self-esteem of students with special educational needs, their anxiety, sensitivity, shyness, as well as lack of flexible curricula and rapid fatigue of these students. Also, some styles of other student's behavior can cause conflicts in inclusive student groups. These include dominance in communication, conservatism in thinking, unreasonable criticism of the communication partner; violation of the partner's personal space; an unexpected speeding of the pace of conversation, the deliberate arranged shortage of time in solving the problem; humiliation of the communication partner's personality and his rights (interruption, ignoring contacts, unwillingness to recognize his rightness in judgments, etc.); constant imposition of their own views; demonstration of their unwillingness to help because of permanent lack of free time; emphasizing the difference with a partner in their favor; insincerity, intemperance, inflexibility, injustice.

Problems related to socio-psychological adaptation to learning in an inclusive student group are quite typical for students with special educational needs. They are specified by the new social situation of development, changing living conditions, their social isolation, their attitude to their own disability and interpersonal relationships. Socio-psychological maladaptation of a student with special educational needs in the group can cause negative

psychogenic reactions, emotional instability, personal and situational anxiety, low self-esteem and low achievement motivation. Therefore, the activity of all employees of higher education institutions is very important for ensuring effective interaction of students with special educational needs in the student group. It should be based on positive emotional self-perception, communication, joint activities of healthy students and students with special educational needs on the basis of tolerance and partnership. All this will help reduce the level of social isolation and, consequently, improve the adaptation of student youth with special educational needs to the conditions of higher education establishment.

As one of the main causes of conflict in inclusive student groups is the socio-psychological features of students with special educational needs, we conducted a diagnostic study among 55 full-time and part-time students with special educational needs who study at Khmelnytskyi National University.

The levels of students' self-esteem were determined by means of the test questionnaire "Self-Assessment Scale" (Kirsheva & Ryabchikova, 1995: 108-112). The questionnaire contains 32 statements with five possible answers: very often - 4 points, often - 3 points, sometimes - 2 points, rarely - 1 point, never - 0 points. In order to determine the level of self-esteem, it is necessary to add points for all 32 statements.

It should be noted that the interpretation of the results of the test-questionnaire "Self-assessment scale" is as follows:

The sum of points from 0 to 43 indicates a high level of self-esteem, at which a person adequately responds to the comments of others and rarely doubts their actions.

The sum of points from 43 to 86 indicates the medium level of self-esteem. Such people rarely suffer from the "inferiority complex" and only from time to time try to adapt to the opinion of others.

The sum of points from 86 to 128 indicates a low level of self-esteem, at which a person reacts painfully to critical remarks addressed to them, always tries to take into account the opinion of others and often suffers from "inferiority complex".

The results of the diagnosis of self-esteem levels of students with special educational needs are presented in Table 1.

Table 1. Self-esteem levels of students with special educational needs

Level	#	%
High	9	16,4
Medium	21	38,2
Low	25	45,4

Source: Authors' own conception

As the results of the study show, the vast majority of students with special educational needs have a low level of self-esteem, which indicates that critical remarks are quite painful for them, they try to adapt to other people's opinions, suffer from excessive shyness, have low motivation for achievements and identification of their professional interests and inclinations. Only 9 students with special educational needs (16.4%) showed a high level of self-esteem, which means they are confident and do not have "inferiority complex" or attempt to adapt to the other's opinions.

The anxiety test (Spielberg Questionnaire) (Nemov, 2001) was used in the diagnostic study to determine the levels of personal (stable personal tendency to respond to social situations with increased anxiety and excitement) and reactive (temporary anxiety in certain life situations) anxiety. The participants were given a questionnaire form with a number of statements to which they had to provide the following answers: 1 – no; 2 – probably so; 3 – true; 4 – really true.

Anxiety levels in the Spielberg Questionnaire are defined as follows:

A score of less than 12 indicates a very low level of anxiety and typical for depressive and areactive state with a low level of motivation.

A score of 0 to 30 indicates low anxiety.

The sum of points from 31 to 45 indicates a medium level of anxiety.

A score of 45 or more indicates a high level of anxiety.

The sum of scores much higher than 46 indicates not only a very high level of anxiety, but also directly correlates with the neurotic conflict, emotional and neurotic breakdowns, psychosomatic diseases.

The results of the study of anxiety levels of the students with special educational needs are represented in Table 2.

Table 2. Anxiety levels of the students with special educational needs.

Levels of manifestation	#	%
Very high	7	12,7
High	15	27,3
Medium	17	31
Low	8	14,5
Very low	3	5,5

Source: Authors' own conception

The results of a study of anxiety levels of students with special educational needs showed that most of them (31%) have a medium level of anxiety. This indicates their tendency to feel fear, apprehension and insecurity in some life situations. Unfortunately, reactive anxiety of 27.3% students with special educational needs transformed into personal anxiety and became their stable personality trait. It should be noted that anxiety not only became a personality trait, but also caused a neurotic conflict, with emotional breakdowns and psychosomatic illnesses of 12.7% students. Only 14.5% of students with special educational needs had a low level of anxiety, which characterizes them as self-confident and calm individuals who do not show fear and apprehension in various life situations. Interestingly, three respondents (5.5%) have a very low level of anxiety. However, it might mean that they are actively suppressing their high anxiety in order to create a good impression of themselves for other people.

In order to further study the socio-psychological characteristics of students with special educational needs, we conducted a test "Assessment of the sociability level" (V. Ryakhovsky) (Karelin, 2007). Students with special educational needs had to fill in the test forms with the answers: "yes" - 2 points, "sometimes" - 1 point, "no" - 0 points. The test results by this method were determined as follows:

30 - 32 points - complete lack of sociable skills. Such people are clearly unsociable and they and their family members usually suffer from it. They are difficult to rely on in a situation that requires team efforts.

25 - 29 points - low sociability. These people are closed, incommunicative, they prefer loneliness, so they have few friends. New work and the need for new contacts disbalance them for a long time. They are aware of this character feature and are often dissatisfied with themselves.

19 - 24 points – a medium level of sociability. Such people are to some extent sociable and in an unknown situation feel quite confident. New

problems do not frighten them. However, they are reluctant to communicate with new people, to take part in disputes and discussions. Their statements tend to be sarcastic, usually with no reason.

14 - 18 points - a sufficient level of sociability. They are inquisitive, willing to listen to an interesting interlocutor, quite patient in communicating with others, defend their point of view without zeal. They meet new people without any worries. At the same time, they do not like noisy companies, eccentric behavior and talkativeness.

9 - 13 points - a high level of sociability. These people are quite sociable, interesting, talkative, they enjoy speaking on various issues, which sometimes irritates others. They are willing to meet new people. They like to be in the center of attention, do not refuse anyone's requests, although they can not always fulfill them. Sometimes they can get angry, but they calm down quickly. They lack perseverance, patience and courage when facing with serious problems.

4 - 8 points – excessive sociability level. Such people are the soul of any company. They enjoy participating in all discussions, although they do not like serious topics. They are ready to talk on any topic, even if they have a superficial idea about it. Everywhere they feel comfortable in all life situations. They settle down to any task, although they may not always be able to successfully complete it. For this reason, managers and colleagues have some apprehension and doubt about them.

3 points or less - supersociable level. The sociability of these people is painful. They are talkative, interfere with some matters that have nothing to do with them. They express their judgements on problems in which they are not competent at. Consciously or unconsciously, they often cause conflicts. They are hot-tempered, offensive, and often biased. Serious work is not for them. Other people find it difficult to deal with them.

The study results on the test "Assessment of the sociability level" (V. Ryakhovsky) are shown in the Table 3.

Table 3. Levels of development of communicative skills and sociability of students with special educational needs

Level of manifestation	#	%
Lack of sociable skills	8	14,5
Low sociability	10	18,2
Medium sociability level	17	31
Sufficient sociability level	15	27,3
High sociability level	4	7,3

Excessive sociability level	1	1,7
Supersociable level	0	0

Source: Authors' own conception

The analysis of the test results showed that only four students (7.3%) with special educational needs have a high sociability level. It was found out that a significant part of respondents has a medium (31%) and sufficient (27.3%) level of sociability. These data indicate that most students with special educational needs are inquisitive, sociable, and patient in communication. A low level of communication skills was diagnosed in 18.2% of students, which indicates that they are closed, lonely, do not want to make new contacts in communication. Unfortunately, eight students with special educational needs (14.5%) totally lack communication skills, i.e. they are unsociable and suffer from it. Only a few students had a high and excessive sociability level. This shows that it is easy for them to make new acquaintances, to express their views on various topics, but they often cause misunderstandings and conflicts with peers, because demonstrating their awareness and success, they do not always complete the work they have started.

We worked out a questionnaire to determine the socialization levels of students with special educational needs. According to the results of the survey, most respondents find it difficult to decide what kind of person they are. Thus 40% of students consider themselves principled, 20% of respondents see themselves as determined, 20% of respondents consider themselves strong-willed and 20% of students say that they are honest people.

As for the relationship with other people, 27.2% of surveyed students easily come into contact with new people. 65.5% students find it difficult to establish new relationships with people. 7.3% of respondents could not answer this question at all.

Answering the question about the frequency of compromising their conscience to achieve their goal, most students admit they often have to do so (41.8%), while 25.5% of respondents say they never compromise their conscience and 32.7% of respondents do it sometimes.

When asked about typical recent ambitions, the majority of respondents answered that they aim for establishing new relationships with interesting people (40%) and professional growth (40%). Only 20% of students are ambitious for making money.

The answers of students with special educational needs about their behaviour in conflict situations appeared to be of great interest. Thus, the

majority of respondents want to get out of the conflict with dignity (56.4%), 23.6% of students go for a compromise solution and 20% of respondents admit they are not inferior to their opponent in the conflict.

Thus, according to the results of the survey among students with special educational needs, we can conclude that most respondents consider themselves principled people, although they do not have a clear idea of what kind of person they are. It was also found out that the vast majority of students find it difficult to establish new relationships with people, though they are ambitious for meeting interesting people and making new friends. The results of the survey also showed that students with special educational needs in a conflict situation attempt to get out of the conflict with dignity, rather than look for compromise solutions.

The K. Thomas test (adaptation by N. Grishina, 2008) was conducted at the end of the diagnostic study to determine the personal disposition of students with special educational needs toward conflict behavior and ways of their behaving in conflict situations. The author of the test K. Thomas identifies the following ways of behaving in conflicts:

- 1) competition as an attempt to satisfy own interests at the expense of others;
- 2) adapting as sacrificing own interests for the benefit of others;
- 3) compromise;
- 4) avoidance as a lack of tendency both for cooperation and for achieving own goals;
- 5) cooperation as working on an alternative solution that fully satisfies the interests of both parties.

The results of the study of behaviors in conflicts of the students with special educational needs are shown in Table 4.

Table 4. Ways of behaving in conflict situations of the students with special educational needs

Ways of behavior	#	%
Competition	10	18,2
Adapting	14	25,5
Compromise	7	12,6
Avoidance	14	25,5
Cooperation	10	18,2

Source: Authors' own conception

As shown in Table 4, adapting (25.5%) and avoidance (25.5%) are typical styles of behavior in conflict situations for most students with special educational needs. It means that they either do not want to defend their rights, do not cooperate with others to avoid conflict, or they agree to accept the views of others sacrificing their own interests. It should be noted that a significant proportion of respondents have directly opposite styles of behavior in conflict situations: 18.2% of respondents seek to protect their own interests in conflict and 18.2% go for cooperation. Unfortunately, only seven students (12.6%) are ready to compromise in conflict situations.

Thus, the obtained data of the conducted diagnostic research became the basis for the development of means of conflict prevention in inclusive student groups. These tools, in our opinion, can be:

- training students to avoid "evaluative stereotypes" while communicating with students with special educational needs, because stereotyping simplifies the process of knowing another person or makes the attitude to them biased;

- development of empathy in interpersonal communication with student with special educational needs. Empathy helps to adequately understand other people. The ability to perceive the feelings of another person as their own and to give an emotional response is a necessary component of communication and a specific means for people to get to know each other.

- developing other students' skills to avoid causal attribution in communication with students with special educational needs. Understanding is often complicated due to the lack of information specifying causal attribution. This phenomenon is the means of interpretation and evaluation of others on the basis of the life experience. Causal attribution involves filling information gaps with characteristics and causes of behavior based on the past experience;

- conducting trainings as effective methods of conflict prevention and resolution in inclusive student groups. Training for students is an effective education model that reproduces the situation of creative search. Training sessions are practical group exercises to develop optimal solutions, application of methods and techniques in artificially created conditions that model a real psychological and pedagogical situation;

- conducting individual interviews to identify unfavorable living and education conditions of students with special educational needs;

- counselling students with special educational needs on overcoming personal problems (misunderstandings with loved ones, arranging of cooperation with other students, etc.);

- involvement of students with special educational needs in the work of the student mutual assistance club, interest club, volunteer activities, etc.

Conclusions and prospects for further research

Thus, the success of educational activities and social adaptation of students with special educational needs in higher education institutions depends on many factors, the main of which are the inclusion of such students in student groups, their involvement in joint activities, their feeling of belonging to the team. It largely depends on the activity of students with special educational needs, their sociability, their range of interests, etc. Teachers' friendly attitude and special training to work in inclusive student groups is a key to successful inclusion of students with special educational needs in the educational environment of higher education institutions.

Social inclusion, in contrast to educational inclusion, is aimed at the social adaptation of young people with special educational needs to the general system of social relations within the educational environment where it takes place. Under the inclusion conditions this category of young people acquire the role behavior of their healthy peers and focuses on joining the educational environment of the academic group, adapting to the requirements of higher education institution and gets support of their studying.

The results of the study reveal the main causes of conflict in inclusive student groups. They are socio-psychological characteristics of students with special educational needs including a low level of self-esteem due to which they get painful experiences because of critical remarks addressed to them, try to adapt to other people's opinions, have low motivation for achievement, feel lonely and anxious; low ability to establish new contacts for communication, low level of sociability; the desire to avoid conflict or to get out of it with dignity, accepting the opinions and interests of others, without seeking compromise solutions. Based on these results, we have developed conflict prevention tools for inclusive student groups that can help students with special educational needs to interact effectively with other students while studying at a higher education institution.

The prospects for further research in this direction are the development and justification of scientific and practical advice to tutors of inclusive student groups to improve educational, socio-psychological and social rehabilitation activities of students with special educational needs during their studies at a higher education institution.

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